

Edward Albee's *The Sandbox*: Disintegration of Family Values and Roles

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Abstract:

The present research paper delves into the family institution depicted in Edward Albee's one-act play *The Sandbox*. It analyses and evaluates the relationships of the family members to each other. It also analyses the performance of their duties and roles in the domestic context. It attempts to weigh the relationship of the members in the family set up. It aims to arrive at the conclusion whether the members cater to the needs of each other or they fail to develop harmonious relationships in the family. Thus, the significance of this research paper lies in its ability to shed light on the institution of family which is seen as citadel of society for a long time. Albee's *The Sandbox* has been a topic of interest among literary critics and researchers for many years. Most of the studies focused on the thematic aspects, features of the absurd theatre and epic theatre. It seems that the institution of family has remained neglected compared to the weightage it must be assigned in the contemporary scenario.

Key Words: Family, Disintegration, Values, Domestic Responsibilities

Introduction:

Edward Albee, the most noted dramatist and director, always focused his plays on the family life of the Americans. He recorded the agonies and disillusionment of the contemporary period in his plays. His plays such as *The Sandbox* (1960), *The American Dream* (1961) and *Who's Afraid of Virginia Woolf?* (1962) delve into the complexities of family divisions and the fabricated family ties in modern American culture (Meserve 356). His plays shocked the audience as well as the critics with their modern themes and experiments. Albee, through his characters, mocks the dysfunctional American families which show no concern to the values of familial aspects such as marriage, parentage, cordial relationships, affection to children etc. Albee's America, especially after the Great Depression and the World Wars, disintegrated socially. There was a mad craving for material success as promised by the great American dream. This was mainly

responsible for the tragic deterioration of the family as an institution of social responsibility. The family tree is denuded of its traditional importance in the wake of rapid material progress in the contemporary times. It can be observed that the old people are neglected and mistreated in many families and are kept in nursing home due to the burden of personal and professional life. It can be also observed that there is a drastic change in the attitudes of the members affecting their relationships in the domestic context.

Albee's one-act play *The Sandbox* focuses on the disintegration of the family, an institution which was once considered the backbone of every success. It portrayed the family's callous reaction to the death of a grandmother. It is dedicated to Albee's grandma Cotter who died in 1959. Albee was greatly attached to his grandmother. In his plays *The Sandbox* and *The American Dream*, Grandma is forced into a living burial and the Young Man helps Grandma depart to another

world. It can be observed that family life is in a very bad shape today. Intolerance is increasing in alarming proportion, reducing the family to consist merely of a husband and a wife who are also poles apart in their aims and objectives. Debusscher has rightly pointed out, “The family is now but an empty myth, a form without content.” Therefore, human relationships are damaged largely with a widening gulf among the members in the family.

The roots of the play *The Sandbox* go very deep in Albee’s adopted family. Albee’s early childhood was spent comfortably and leisurely. However, the problems started in his adolescent age. He witnessed loveless attitude of his parents towards each other. At the age of 21, he separated from his adopted parents and spent a decade in Greenwich village living off a trust his maternal grandmother had left him in 1949. In *The Sandbox*, Albee has used a process of depersonalization of characters which is at the center of The Theatre of Absurd. The characters are not named and they are recognized by their functions such as Mommy, Daddy, Grandma, Young Man and Musician. Their names are empty of affection, pointing to the pre-senility and vacuity of their characters. The family depicted here consists of Mommy, Daddy and Grandma. Mommy is a harsh and tyrannical woman of fifty-five. Daddy, Mommy’s husband, is a frail but well-off man of sixty. Grandma, Mommy’s mother, is a withered and emaciated woman of eighty-six. In the foregoing part of this research paper, the relationships of the members are analyzed and evaluated to make valid comment on the institution of family.

Marriage and Husband-Wife Relationship:

The concept of marriage has rendered stability to the society since ancient times. However, today it is largely degenerated and is regarded as a means of social upliftment and

economic security. Instead of looking for suitable matches, girls look for partners who could bring enormous wealth and put it in their possession. Mommy, Grandma’s daughter, has married to Daddy only for the sake of money. Grandma herself is not happy about her daughter’s marriage to Daddy. She says, “that’s what she married. Rich? I tell you... money, money, money.” (Albee)

Daddy and Mommy, the husband and the wife, are unable to get in touch with one another because they have nothing substantial to say. There is no sense of domesticity between Mommy and Daddy. There is no meaningful interaction between the two. They communicate with each other briefly. Daddy cannot think anything new. Mommy talks to her husband in cliches. She only gives curt replies to him. She seems to be not at all interested in him. She is a very commanding wife who has a peremptory tone of voice. This is the reason that she does not have a genuine conversation with her husband. The lack of communication between the two is apparent in the following dialogue.

DADDY (After a pause). Shall we talk to each other?

MOMMY (with that little laugh; picking something off her dress). Well, you can talk, if you want to... if you can think of anything to say... if you can think of anything new.

DADDY (thinks). No... I suppose not.

MOMMY (with a triumphant laugh). Of course not! (Albee)

Thus, Daddy is subdued for years in his marital life. He is submissive and obedient. He remains calm and silent most of the time. He is incapable of coming up with anything meaningful to say. He often agrees with his wife’s opinion by saying, “Whatever you say, Mommy.” (Albee) Mommy gets pleasure from Daddy’s helpless inexpressibility. Thus, the husband and the wife

do not really engage in any genuine conversation. Their talk is devoid of emotional significance. They behave just like robots programmed to utter words without any emotional attachments.

The Sandbox also criticizes unproductiveness in marriage. Mommy and Daddy are childless and there is nothing that could hold them together. Albee shows that marriage is an institution which has been drained of love and affection. William H. Chafe, in an article “Women and American Society” has rightly given alarming figures about the deterioration in American family life.

Mother-Daughter Relationship:

Grandma and Mommy, the mother and daughter, do not have genuine communicate with each other. Mommy has brought Grandma to her house in the city for money only. She has sold the property of Grandma and placed her in a small place. She has provided her only an army blanket. She serves Grandma in a separate dish reserved for her. She is empty of love and affection for Grandma. She does not care for her at all. She does not show any concern for her. She pretends that she is saddened by Grandma’s imminent death. Grandma is dumped mercilessly into the sandbox to die alone. She mocks her daughter’s pretentious attempts to appear grief-stricken:

MOMMY (barely able to talk). It means the time has come for poor Grandma... and I can’t bear it!

DADDY (vacantly). I... I suppose you’ve got to be brave.

GRANDMA (Mocking). That’s right, kid; be brave. You’ll bear up; you’ll get over it.

(Albee)

When Grandma pretends that she is dead, Mommy shows her most inhuman side. She says, “So it is! Our long night is over. We must put away our tears, take off our mourning... and find the future. It’s our duty. (Albee) Thus, Mommy is

a callous person. She is insensitive towards her husband as well as her own mother.

Grandma: The Representative of Family Values:

Grandma can be called citadel of the family depicted in *The Sandbox*. Only she appears to have a sense of family life. Her devotion to her family is seen in her refusal to marry again after the death of her husband. She stands as the representative of the old moral values which are disintegrating day-by-day in the contemporary times. She recollects the hardships which she faced in rearing Mommy, her daughter. Her husband died when she was only thirty years old. She recounts her maternal responsibilities. She remembers that it was very terrible to raise Mommy. She says, “(indicates MOMMY) I had to raise that big cow over there all by my lonesome. You can imagine what that was like. Lordy!” (Albee) Grandma did everything for the sake of her daughter. However, she did not get good treatment from her own daughter. She accepts her lot in the final stage of her life.

Grandma points out her vulnerable condition. She summarizes her life in terms of relationships and lack of respect for her. Her remarks expose the vacuity of American family life. She says, “Honestly! What a way to treat an old woman! Drag her out of the house... stick her in a car... bring her out here from the city... dump her in a pile of sand... and leave her here to set.” (Albee) Mommy and Daddy show their dehumanizing behaviour in their act of putting Grandma mercilessly into a sandbox. They are insensitive towards Grandma’s pains. They remain motionless at a distant. As Grandma approaches death, she receives kind and affectionate treatment from the Young Man who kisses her on the forehead. In the final scene, Grandma accepts her lot with a smiling face. Thus, she is the representative of many old people

who welcome death as a better substitute of life which is devoid of love and affections in the familial context.

Conclusion:

Thus, it can be said that Albee, through this one-act play, seems to hint the great social threat in the disintegration of the family institution. *The Sandbox* presents a true-to-life picture of the American society. It presents a pathetic picture of human beings as they grow old and approach death. Albee points out the worse conditions in America through the instances of inhuman treatment to the elderly people. He puts emphasis on the fact that tending to the elderly people carries a moral duty. He renders universality through nameless characters and suggests that this could happen in any part of the universe. The family members neglect their moral responsibilities and duties in the rapidly progressing American society. Thus, the present research paper points out the decline of loving

family relationships and disintegration of family values and roles in Albee's play *The Sandbox*.

References:

1. Albee, Edward. *The Sandbox*. Dramatists Play Service, Inc. 1959.
2. Yadav, Renu. "Description of Death: A Recurring Theme in the Works of Edward Albee." *Novateur Publications*. vol. 7, Issue 6, June 2021, pp. 420-424.
3. Babashekh, Gazang Saedgul. "Dehumanization in Edward Albee's Play *The Sandbox*." *Journal of the University of Garmian* 6 (2), 2019, pp. 339-342.
4. Arnul Ananad, J. "Edward Albee: A Playwright with a Purpose." *Notions* 2017, vol. VIII, no. 2, 2017, pp. 108-115.
5. Christian, Reka M. "End-life Crisis in Edward Albee's *The Sandbox* and *The American Dream*." *Cultural Perspectives* 26/2021. pp. 53-72.